

INVESTIGATION OF PROCESS-RELATED DAMAGE DURING THERMAL PIERCING OF A THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

N.W.A. Brown^{1,2*}, C.M. Worrall¹, A. Kapadia¹, S.L. Ogin², P.A. Smith²

¹ Joining Technologies Group, TWI Ltd, Cambridge, UK,

² Department of Mechanical Engineering Sciences, University of Surrey, Guildford, UK

* Corresponding author (nick.brown@twi.co.uk)

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1 Introduction

Over the last decade, Fibre Reinforced Plastics (FRPs) have seen further significant uptake into structural applications within the aerospace, automotive and energy sectors. The primary drivers for this increase in FRP use are the specific properties (i.e. strength and stiffness to weight ratios) that are achieved when compared to conventional materials. Despite the mechanical advantages that can be gained by using FRPs instead of conventional materials, there are still many barriers that prevent this step change being implemented by some industry sectors. One of these barriers is the cost and complexity of manufacturing and processing FRPs.

Advances in polymer technology have led to extensive development of high performance Thermoplastic Composites (TPCs) which not only exhibit mechanical properties comparable to Thermosetting Composites (TSCs), but can be formed and pressed under heating using similar approaches to sheet metal processing techniques. These rapid production and processing techniques are enabling TPCs to enter high production rate industry sectors (e.g. automotive) that were previously not favoured for TSCs. It is almost inevitable that TPC components will need to be joined, either to each other or to other materials. As with thermosetting composites, the introduction of holes or cut-outs for mechanical fastening leads to associated challenges.

Machining holes for mechanical fastening of composites is a significant issue within the composites industry and is still fraught with problems. Current machining processes include, among others, conventional drilling, laser machining and abrasive water-jet cutting. These are all material

removal processes that rely on cutting the fibres and matrix to create a hole. Cutting fibres in this way removes the load transfer paths in this region, to the detriment of structural performance.

Conventional drilling is currently the most commonly employed material removal technique. It is a relatively inexpensive method of machining holes (when compared to laser or water-jet machining) that can be used on large, non flat, structures without significant complications. Despite this, the damage inflicted on a composite structure when drilling holes gives rise to stress concentrations that reduce the mechanical performance. If drilling parameters are not carefully selected and controlled then delaminations, at the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate, and degradation of the hole wall can result from the drilling process [1-3]. These problems provide a need for research into new methods and processes that can lead to cost savings via weight reductions, processing time reductions or fewer part rejections.

As an alternative to machining, material displacement processes can be applied to composites to create holes for fastening without removing the load carrying fibres from the structure. Moulding-in holes is a method used to displace fibres around an insert and into the surrounding volume to retain the load carrying fibre paths. The retention of fibre continuity around the hole permits higher notched and bearing strength through a reduction in stress concentrations around the hole when compared to conventional drilling [4] [5].

Thermal piercing is another material displacement process that can be used to displace fibres around a hole in TPCs at various stages of manufacture or subsequent processing [6]. In this process, multiple

interactions occur between the piercing pin and the composite laminate which will damage fibres, affect (local) fibre architecture and volume fraction, and influence hole surface quality. In this regard, the aim of the present study is to determine the feasibility of a thermal piercing technique to replace conventional machining processes for producing holes in TPCs. Specifically, an investigation has been undertaken into the variables associated with a thermal piercing process. The process is used to produce holes in post manufacture TPC parts for mechanical fastening.

The structure of the paper is as follows. First the results are reported from feasibility trials in which the notched strength of thermally pierced specimens is compared with conventionally drilled specimens. Following this preliminary study, an instrumented piercing rig was designed, which enables the force-displacement response to be monitored during the penetration process. Initial results are presented which enable the load-displacement response to be compared for different spike angles.

2 Feasibility Trials

Feasibility trials were undertaken to assess the ability of the thermal piercing technique to produce holes in a TPC. The three stage technique consisted of a heating stage, with the laminate under a restraining pressure (Fig. 1a.), a piercing stage (Fig. 1b.) and a cooling stage, under continued restraining pressure (Fig. 1c).

The experimental set-up comprised a compression system to restrain through thickness expansion of the laminate when it was locally heated, a heat input in the form of an induction coil and a pneumatically driven piercing spike. Once the laminate was at the required temperature ($\sim 350^{\circ}\text{C}$) the locally molten area of the laminate was pierced.

A cross ply, continuous carbon fibre reinforced Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite was used for the experiments. With a melting temperature of 343°C the laminates were locally heated to above their melting temperature ($\sim 350^{\circ}\text{C}$) before piercing. The laminates were 2.1 mm thick and pierced using a 6 mm diameter, untreated, stainless steel spike with a 30° spike angle (Fig. 2).

The notched tensile strength of the thermally pierced laminates was compared with conventionally drilled specimens (Fig. 3). The tests were conducted according to ASTM 5766/D5766M. The resultant notched strength of the specimens was approximately 8% stronger than the conventionally drilled specimen strengths.

The thermally pierced specimens were sectioned and polished across the diameter of the hole (Fig. 4) to reveal the hole internal surface and the resultant laminate structure after piercing. Using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Zeiss 1455EP) there was significant damage seen as a consequence of the piercing process (Fig. 5, 6). Large regions of fibre fracture were seen around the hole surface due to the interaction with the piercing spike as it travelled through the laminate. There was also considerable ply distortion around the hole edge where molten material was forced away from the hole region. This material would have been molten during the initial period of piercing. Since the heat input was deactivated immediately prior to heating, the laminate is constantly cooling whilst the piercing spike is travelling through the laminate. Therefore, matrix cracking can occur at the hole edge where the laminate temperature has locally reduced to below its melting temperature while the spike is continuing to displace material (Fig. 7).

3 Instrumented Piercing

Subsequent to the feasibility trials, instrumented piercing tests were conducted to evaluate the force-displacement characteristics of various spike geometries. The experimental set-up was modified from the feasibility trials to enable measurement of both the resisting force on the spike and the displacement of the spike through the laminate. The set-up can be broken into three main parts: the clamping system, the heating system and the instrumented piercing system (Fig. 8).

The clamping system was a manufactured steel frame that allowed the clamping force (applied pneumatically) to be transmitted around the instrumented piercing system and onto the laminate surface. The method of heating, as mentioned previously, was via induction that could provide low heat up times within susceptor materials. Cross-ply, continuous carbon fibres were used here, so the

laminates could undergo induction heating relatively easily. With induction as the heating method, the clamping system included two ceramic blocks that were used to apply pressure onto the composite. This prevented the clamping surfaces heating more rapidly than the composite, which would occur if the clamping material was a susceptor metal. The piercing system uses a pneumatic cylinder, housed within the clamping frame (Fig. 9), to drive the instrumented piercing spike through the laminate when molten. The system records the resistive force data and the displacement of the spike.

The instrumented piercing experiments were carried out in a similar way to the trials. First the laminates were clamped under pneumatic pressure before being locally heated to above their melting temperature ($\sim 350^{\circ}\text{C}$). Once the target temperature had been reached, the piercing spike was driven through the laminate while measuring the resistive force and corresponding displacement of the spike. The spike diameter was 6 mm and constructed from untreated stainless steel (as used previously). For the instrumented piercing, three different spike geometries were used with spike angles of 20° , 30° and 40° . Cooling under pressure and ambient conditions was continued until the laminate was below the glass transition temperature and the spike was removed prior to releasing the clamping pressure.

The force and displacement measurements were taken for two sets of instrumented piercing experiments for each spike geometry. The individual spike geometry plots for the 20° , 30° and 40° spike geometries (Fig. 10, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 respectively) were plotted to show their relationship to the spike length (determined by the spike angle).

Similar features can be seen in the force-displacement plots for all spike geometries tested. The initial piercing stage of the process is shown by a non-linear increase in force as the spike makes contact with the top of the laminate. The contact area continues to increase as the spike tip progresses through the laminate and results in the increasing resistive force measured.

The spike tip will exit the back of the laminate as the displacement increases further. This leads to a

change in the contact area and a modification of the force-displacement curve.

The force then reaches a maximum before reducing. The point at which the peak force occurs appears to be at a value of displacement at which the parallel sides of the piercing spike meet the top surface of the laminate (indicated with a dashed line on Fig. 10, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12).

After the maximum force, the parallel sides of the spike are beginning to enter the top of the laminate. The parallel sides provide no contribution to the projected contact area between the spike and the laminate. Therefore, from this point onwards the projected contact area is decreasing while the spike continues to exit the back of the laminate. This is associated with a reduction in resistive force on the spike with increasing displacement (Fig. 10, Fig. 11 and Fig. 12).

Subsequently, the spike will fully exit the back of the laminate and the parallel sides of the spike pin will remain as the only contact region between the outside of the spike and the inside of the hole. At this point the projected contact area has reduced to zero and the measured force is principally due to the friction between the spike surface and the hole wall.

Comparing the force-displacement data for the three spike geometries shows that the spike geometry influences the peak force during piercing and the corresponding displacement at which it occurs (Fig. 13). For the sharpest spike geometry, 20° , the peak force measured is lower than the force measured for the 30° spike, which in turn is lower than the force for the largest spike angle of 40° . This trend is expected since the projected area in contact with the laminate is directly related to the spike angle. Reducing the spike angle will, therefore, reduce the maximum projected contact area between the spike and the laminate and lead to a reduction in maximum resistive force on the spike (Fig. 13).

The location of the peak force is also governed by the geometry of the spike. The length of the conical section of the spike (before the spike becomes parallel) will be determined by the spike angle. For smaller spike angles, this length will be increased and the peak force will be experienced at a larger

displacement than for larger spike angles. This expected trend can be seen in the data (Fig. 13) where the peak force is not only lower for the 20° spike, but also occurs at a larger displacement than for the 30° spike. The same trend is apparent when comparing the data for the 30° and 40° spikes.

After the spike emerged from the back face of the laminate and only frictional forces were measured, it seemed reasonable to assume that the frictional force should be the same for all three spike geometries, since the shaft diameter is the same in each case. The measured data does not support this, however, and can be seen to show varying frictional values (Fig. 13) in this final stage. This may be because of elastic contraction of the hole around the spike. The heat input was deactivated upon piercing so the laminate continued to reduce in temperature for the duration of the piercing stages. For larger spike angles the spike length is shorter and, hence, the piercing process occurs over a smaller displacement of the spike. For a constant spike displacement rate, this reduction in vertical displacement will decrease the time for the piercing process to be completed. The shorter time means that the laminate will not locally cool to the same extent as for piercing with sharper spike geometries. This would allow more viscous flow of the higher temperature matrix and result in a reduced elastic contraction around the spike and a lower final frictional force, as seen in Fig. 13.

The effect of matrix cooling over the piercing process may also be manifested in the total work done by the spike to produce the hole (Table. 1). The work done, derived from the area under the load-displacement curves (from initial piercing to the exit of the conical spike section at the back face), reduces for increasing spike angle. Since the matrix does not cool to the same extent when piercing with a larger spike angle, it remains less viscous and requires less work to displace when compared with smaller spike angle geometries.

4 Concluding Remarks

Initial feasibility trials have shown that an increase in tensile notched strength of 8% can be achieved for thermally pierced laminates when compared to conventionally drilled laminates. To investigate the parameters involved in the thermal piercing process,

an instrumented rig has been designed to enable the load-displacement response to be monitored during piercing. Preliminary experiments have shown that the piercing process consists of the following distinct phases:

- Initial piercing of the laminate with the spike tip progressing through the thickness
- A secondary stage, where the spike tip has emerged from the back face of the laminate and the resistive force on the spike appears approximately linear with spike displacement
- Immediately prior to the parallel sides of the spike reaching the top surface of the laminate the peak resistive force on the spike is reached
- The spike exits from the back face of the laminate, reducing the resistive force on the spike due to decreasing projected contact area
- Frictional sliding occurs between the parallel sides of the spike and the hole wall once the spike has fully exited the laminate.

A smaller spike angle leads to a smaller maximum resistive force on the spike. The spike angle also dictates the spike length, which governs the location of the maximum resistive force in the force-displacement results.

Future work will include an investigation of the effects of thermal piercing spike angles on the strength of the laminates.

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6 References

- [1] R. Zitouné and F. Collombet "Numerical prediction of the thrust force responsible of delamination during drilling of the long-fibre composite structures". *Composites: Part A*, 38, pp. 858-866, 2006.
- [2] J. Ramkumar, S. Aravindan, S. K. Malhotra and R. Krishnamurthy "An enhancement of the machining performance of GFRP by oscillatory assisted

drilling”. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 23, pp. 240-244, 2003.

- [3] A. M. Abrao, P. E. Faria, J. C. C. Rubio, P. Reis and J. P. Davim “Drilling of fiber reinforced plastics: A review”. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 186, pp. 1-7, 2006.
- [4] L. W. Chang, S. S. Yau and T. W. Chou “Notched strength of woven fabric composites with moulded-in holes”. *Composites*, 18, 3, pp. 233-241, 1987.
- [5] W. Hufenbach, R. Gottwald and R. Kupfer “Bolted joints with moulded holes for textile thermoplastic composites”. *Proceedings of ICCM 18*; Korea, M06-2, pp. 1-6, 2011.
- [6] W. Hufenbach, F. Adam and R. Kupfer “A novel notching technique for bolted joints in textile-reinforced thermoplastic composites”. *Proceedings of ECCM 14*; Hungary, Paper ID 461, pp. 1-9, 2010.

Fig. 1. Schematic of 3 stage thermal piercing process.

Fig. 2. Schematic of 30° piercing spike.

Fig. 3. Normalised tensile notched strength.

Fig. 4. Schematic of specimen sectioning for microscopy

Fig. 5. SEM micrograph of hole wall (1)

Fig. 6. SEM micrograph of hole wall (2)

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of hole edge with resultant laminate structure.

Fig. 8. Schematic of instrumented piercing set up.

Fig. 9. Photograph of instrumented piercing test rig.

Fig. 10. Force-displacement of 20° spike thermal piercing.

Fig. 11. Force-displacement of 30° spike thermal piercing.

Fig. 12. Force-displacement of 40° spike thermal piercing.

Table. 1. Approximate average work done for thermal piercing with various spike geometries.

Spike Angle (°)	Approximate Total Work Done(J)
20	8.7
30	7.4
40	4.6

Fig. 13. Force-displacement of thermal piercing with various spike geometries.